

OLONITE PROPORTIONAL ALLOCATION METHOD AND THE THEORY OF SETS: THE RELEVANCES WITHIN

Oluyemi Ayodele OLONITE

Email: oluyemiolonite@hotmail.com

Mobile No: +2347062205843

Research Portfolios: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Oluyemi-Olonite-2>
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2785-2337>

ABSTRACT

Olonite Proportional Allocation Method (OPAM) is a method used to allocate sample to strata based on the strata variances and similar sampling in the strata. An Olonite allocation scheme provides the most precision for estimating a population mean given a fixed total sample. it can be used to select sample from Organizations, Countries, States that has scattered branches. It was developed as a solution to the short comings of the Bowler's Proportional Allocation Method. The OPAM advocates for the use of the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) to sample from each stratum of a strata. In this case, the strata can be seen an Organization, State, Country, etc while the stratum represents departments, Cities, States respectively, etc. OPAM asserts that the higher the population, the higher the sample should be per branch, departments, etc, this will give an average equal representation for each stratum to be considered and selected. The Olonite Proportional Allocation Method helps to reduce time wastage while trying to appropriate a perfect set i.e. Organizations having the same no of departments and staff. Olonite Allocation is always the best proportional allocation method (since Olonite Allocation is optimal).

Keywords: Proportional Allocation Method, Olonite Diagram, OD, OPAM, Theory of Sets, Statistics, Olonite Proportional Allocation Method, Bowler's Proportional Allocation Method, Olonite Sampling Technique, OST

INTRODUCTION

A population can be stratified using a reliable sampling method, however, a strata relies on the stratum for its sampling and this is as a result that a stratum is a subset of a strata. There have been some known allocation methods currently in use but like the shortcomings in some sampling

methods which led to the development of the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST), the Olonite Proportional Allocation Method (OPAM) was developed to fill the gaps identified in this know and widely used Sampling Techniques and Allocation Methods.

Sampling from a population can be equivalent to the theory of set by George Cantor. According to George Cantor, the universal set is the set of all sets. All sets are therefore subsets of the universal set.

Venn diagrams are used to represent sets. Here, the set $A\{1, 2, 4, 8\}$ is shown using a circle. In Venn diagrams, sets are usually represented using circles. The universal set is the rectangle. The set A is a subset of the universal set and so it is within the rectangle.

Figure 1: Venn diagram 1

Source: revisionmaths.com, 2021

The complement of A , written A' , contains all events in the sample space which are not members of A . A and A' together cover every possible eventuality.

Figure 2: Venn diagram 2

Source: revisionmaths.com, 2021

The Olonite Proportional Allocation Method advocates for the use of the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) to sample from a Stratum to get the total sampling size. It was deduced that OPAM supports the theory of sets have a Universal Set, Subset, Null Set, Superset, etc. The Organization represents the Universal Set of which the branches represents either Subset, Null Set, Superset, etc.

The Olonite Proportional Allocation Method (OPAM) Versions are thus:

Figure 3: Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 1

Source: Author’s Computation and Design, 2021

Olonite Diagrams are used to represent a complete set. Here, the Branch A[100, 10, 58, 20], B[100, 10, 58, 20], C[100, 10, 58, 20] and D[100, 10, 58, 20] is shown using a Rectangle. In the Olonite Diagrams, branches are usually represented using Rectangles. The Organisation O is the Oval shape. The Branch A, B, C and D is a Subset of the Organisation O, the figures: 100, 10, 58 and 20 in each branch (A, B, C and D) represents the sub population in the departments.

For example, in the Operations Department there are 100 staff, Legal Department has 10 staff, the Human Resources Department has 58 staff while the Finance and Accounts Department has 20 Staff. This made a total population of 188 for each branch and since the Organization has the exact number of departments and staff, this represents a perfect set with multiple branch

Figure 4: Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 2

Source: Author's Computation and Design, 2021

In this second Version, Olonite Diagrams are used to represent a complete set. Here, the Branch A[45, 7, 20], B[46, 10, 21], and C[23, 14, 18, 20] is shown using a Rectangle. In the Olonite Diagrams, branches are usually represented using Rectangles. The Organisation X is the Oval shape. The Branch A, B, and C is a Subset of the Organisation X, the figures: 45, 7, 20; 46, 10, 21, and 23, 14, 18, 20 in each branch (A, B and C) represents the sub population in each departments.

For example, in the Operations Department for Branch A, there are 45 staff, Legal Department has 7 staff, while the Human Resources Department has 20 staff. In the Operations Department for Branch B, there are 46 staff, Legal Department has 10 staff, while the Human Resources Department has 21. In the Operations Department for Branch C, there are 23 staff, Legal Department has 14 staff, the Human Resources Department has 18 staff while the Finance and Accounts Department has 20 Staff. This made a total population of 72, 77 and 75 respectively for each branch and since the Organization has different number of departments and staff, this does not represent a perfect set.

Figure 5: Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 3

Source: Author's Computation and Design, 2021

Olonite Diagrams are used to represent a complete set. Here, the Branch A[100, 10, 58, 20], is shown using a Rectangle. In the Olonite Diagrams, branches are usually represented using Rectangles. The Organisation Z is the Oval shape. The Branch A is a Subset of the Organisation Z, the figures: 100, 10, 58 and 20 in the branch A represents the sub population in the departments.

For example, in the Operations Department there are 100 staff, Legal Department has 10 staff, the Human Resources Department has 58 staff while the Finance and Accounts Department has 20 Staff. This made a total population of 188 for each branch and since the Organization has the exact number of departments and staff, this represents a perfect set with a branch.

Figure 6: Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 4

Source: Author's Computation and Design, 2021

The complement of Y, written Y^1 , contains all events in the sample space which are not members of I, J, K and L. I, J, K and L and Y^1 together cover every possible eventuality.

Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 4 informs that an organisation having more branches having the same number of department and staff while the headquarters department and staff slightly differs to all the branch can be represented with the OD Complete Set 4.

Figure 7: Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 5

Source: Author's Computation and Design, 2021

The complement of P, written P^1 , contains all events in the sample space which are not members of M, N and O. M, N, and O and P^1 together cover every possible eventuality.

Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 4 informs that an organisation having more branches having the same number of department and staff while the headquarters department and staff slightly differs to all the branch can be represented with the OD Complete Set 5.

2. EMPIRICAL REVIEW OF LITERATURES

The desired information about the population and its precision is based on a stratified sample in stratified sampling, which depends on the size of samples in different strata. The sample size in different strata is being fixed in advance scientifically by the experimenter. The guiding principal in the determination of the n_i , the stratum sample size is to choose them in such a way as to estimate the mean on the desired information with the desired precision for a minimum cost or with maximum precision for a given cost, thus making the most effective use of the resources available. The allocation of the sample to different strata made in accordance with this principle is called the principle of optimum allocation (Sukhatme, Sukhatme, Sukhatme and Asoke, 1984).

The intuitively obvious points for optimum allocation are:

1. The large size of stratum, the larger should be the size of the sample to be selected from it.
2. The larger the variability within a stratum, the larger should be the size of the sample from it, and
3. The cheaper the cost per unit in a stratum, the larger should be the size of the sample from that stratum.

In Achonu, Okoro & Ozomadu, (2019) on the relationship between authoritative classroom management style and the performance of students in public secondary schools in Imo State. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised all the teachers and students of public secondary schools in Imo State (212123). A sample size of 399 was arrived at through Taro Yamane sample size determination technique. The researcher adopted questionnaire as instrumentation for the study. The data which was generated from the questionnaire was analyzed using modified four point Likert type scale, Pearson Correlation coefficient, standard deviation statistics was used to test the hypothesis because of the large sample size.

Sample Size Proportion Allocation adopted by Achonu, Okoro & Ozomadu, (2019)

To assign the sample size of 399 to the respondents, the researcher employed the Bourley's proportional allocation formula (see Table 2.1): $n_b = n(n)/N$; Where: n_b = Bourley Proportional Allocation Formula, n = Population allocated to respondent groups, n = Total sample size, N = Population of the study. The determination of each of the sample group is shown in Table 2.1:

Table 2.1. Sampling Distribution using Bourley's Proportional Allocation Technique

Study Under Study	Population Frequency	Sample Size Distribution Using Bourley's Technique
Okigwe Zone I	14856	nb = 28
Okigwe Zone II	17377	nb = 33
Orlu Zone I	42013	nb = 79
Orlu Zone II	26073	nb = 49
Owerri Zone I	75883	nb = 143
Owerri Zone II	35921	nb = 67
OVERALL TOTAL	212123	399

Source: Field Survey, 2018 (Record and Statistics Unit SEMB Imo State) retrieved from Achonu, Okoro & Ozomadu, (2019)

In Achonu, Okoro & Ozomadu, (2019), the population of the study comprised of all the teachers and students of public secondary schools in Imo State (212123). A sample size of 399 was arrived at through Taro Yamane sample size determination technique. The sample size is seen to be extremely low using the Taro Yamane Sampling Method and this fails to go with the allocation of the sample to different strata made in accordance with the principle of optimum

allocation as submitted in Sukhatme, Sukhatme, Sukhatme & Asoke, (1984) as thus: The intuitively obvious points for optimum allocation are:

1. The large size of stratum, the larger should be the size of the sample to be selected from it.
2. The larger the variability within a stratum, the larger should be the size of the sample from it, and
3. The cheaper the cost per unit in a stratum, the larger should be the size of the sample from that stratum.

Using the Taro Yamane Sampling Method made wrong the Bourley's Proportional Allocation Technique which means that once a Sampling Technique gives inaccurate sampling size, the allocation method will definitely give twice a wrong result; therefore the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) and the Olonite Proportional Allocation Method (OPAM) are advised since they are both seen to be an Optimal Technique and Method.

Table 2.2. Sampling Distribution using the Olonite Sampling Technique to determine the sample size and the Olonite Proportional Allocation Method for the Sample Size Distribution of the same data set in Table 2.1:

Study Under Study	Population Frequency	Sample Size Distribution Using Olonite Proportional Allocation Method
Okigwe Zone I	14856	$O_1 = 13932$
Okigwe Zone II	17377	$O_2 = 16297$
Orlu Zone I	42013	$O_3 = 39401$
Orlu Zone II	26073	$O_4 = 24452$
Owerri Zone I	75883	$O_5 = 71166$
Owerri Zone II	35921	$O_6 = 33688$
OVERALL TOTAL	212123	198,936

Source: Author's Computation (2021), Field Survey, 2018 (Record and Statistics Unit SEMB Imo State) retrieved from Achonu, Okoro and Ozomadu, (2019)

Calculation of the Sample Size using the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST)

Olonite Sampling Technique advocate for the use of the Category 1, Version 3 of the OST for population ranging from 160,001 – 3,200,000 thus:

$$SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL(\%) - OCL(\%))^5}$$

Note: SS = Sampling Size

TP = Total Population

1 = Booster or Step-down

μ = Stochastic Error

^{3,4,5,6 and 7} = Multiplier

TCL = Total Confidence Level

OCL = Observed Confidence Level

SS = ?

TP = 212123

Multiplier = 5

TCL = 100%

OCL = 95%

$\mu = 5\% = 5/100 = 0.05$

$$SS = \frac{212121}{1 + 212123(100\% - 95\%)^5} = \frac{212121}{1 + 212123(0.05)^5}$$

$$SS = \frac{212121}{1 + 212123(0.00000003125)} = \frac{212121}{1 + 0.066288437}$$

$$SS = \frac{212121}{1 + 0.066288437} = \frac{212121}{1.066288437}$$

SS = 198,935.8 (When the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number).

SS = 198,936

Calculation of the Distribution Size using the Olonite Proportional Allocation Method

(OPAM)

Olonite Proportional Allocation Method “Formulae”: $O_a = \frac{TSS_a(GP)}{TP}$

$$O_{a1} = \frac{198936(14856)}{212123} = \frac{2955393216}{212123} = 13932.4 = 13932.$$

$$O_{a2} = \frac{198936(17377)}{212123} = \frac{3456910872}{212123} = 16296.7 = 16297.$$

$$O_{a3} = \frac{198936(42013)}{212123} = \frac{835789168}{212123} = 39401.1 = 39401.$$

$$O_{a4} = \frac{198936(26073)}{212123} = \frac{5186858328}{212123} = 24452.1 = 24452.$$

$$O_{a5} = \frac{198936(75883)}{212123} = 71165.5 = 71166.$$

$$O_{a6} = \frac{198936(35921)}{212123} = \frac{7145980056}{212123} = 33687.9 = 33688.$$

As seen in the Olonite Sampling Technique and the Olonite Proportional Allocation Method calculation above in compare with the Taro Yamane and Bourley’s proportional allocation, the results of the Sample Size and its Distributions differ which shows that OST and OPAM give the optimal result. Check table 2.1 and 2.2.

Also, a second procedure can be adhered to following the stages listed below depending on the size of the population and the sample size to be achieved:

3. METHODOLOGY

This Methodology shows the procedures and structure to be followed using the Olonite Proportional Allocation Method (OPAM) with the second approach.

3.1. PROCEDURES/STAGES

The First procedure: Study the organization to know the version of the Olonite Set Diagram that best fit into the organization settings.

The Second Procedure: Apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the branches to sample.

For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001,

$$SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$$

For population ranging between 1 – 8,000 (Which is the most widely used)

The Third Procedure: After the branches sample has been gotten, apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the departments to sample.

For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001,

$$SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$$

The Fourth Procedure: After the department sample has been gotten, apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the number of staff to sample.

For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001,

$$SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$$

The Fifth Procedure: After the staff sample has been gotten,

- i. apply the no of sample gotten to the other related department as in the Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 1, however,

- ii. if the departments and staff have different numbers (not equal), then the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) should be applicable to each departments and staff unlike the “i” in the fifth Procedure and added together to get the total sample size.

3.2. UNDERSTANDING THE PROCEDURES/STAGES OF OLONITE DIAGRAM REPRESENTING THE COMPLETE SET 1

For example: An organization O has 4 branches; A, B, C and D (Operations, Finance and Accounts, Human Resources and legal) having 100, 10, 58 and 20 staff respectively. The number of staff in each department of each branch are the same, therefore, the Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 1 is valid for organization O and the procedures/stages 1 – 5 should be followed.

As a researcher you are to sample from organization O total population which has 188 population. Directly sampling from the 188 total population will not give equal representation hence the Five (5) procedures/stages is advised as seen below:

Table 1: The Five Tabulated Stages of Olonite Proportional Allocation Method for the Olonite Diagram 1

Stages	To Do 1	To Do 2
The First procedure:	Study the organization to know the version of the Olonite Diagram that best fit into the organization settings.	Check which of the Olonite Diagrams best fit the organization in view
The Second Procedure:	Apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the branches to sample.	4 Branches (A, B, C and D) $SS = \frac{4}{1 + 4(0.05)^3} = \frac{4}{1 + 4(0.000125)}$ $= \frac{4}{1 + 0.005} = \frac{4}{1.005}$ $= 3.99$

	<p>For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001,</p> $SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$ <p>For population ranging between 1 – 8,000 (Which is the most widely used)</p>	<p>$SS = \underline{4}$</p> <p>OPAM suggests the use of all the four branches since the OST result give 3.99 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p>
The Third Procedure:	<p>After the branches sample has been gotten, apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the departments to sample.</p> <p>For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001,</p> $SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$ <p>For population ranging between 1 – 8,000 (Which is the most widely used)</p>	<p>4 Departments (Operations, Finance and Accounts, Human Resources and legal), Branch A.</p> $SS = \frac{4}{1 + 4(0.05)^3} = \frac{4}{1 + 4(0.000125)}$ $= \frac{4}{1 + 0.005} = \frac{4}{1.0005}$ <p>= 3.99</p> <p>$SS = \underline{4}$</p> <p>OPAM suggests the use of all the four departments since the OST result give 3.99 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p>
The Fourth Procedure:	<p>After the department sample has been gotten, apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the number of staff to sample.</p> <p>For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001,</p>	<p>Operations Staff: 100:</p> $SS = \frac{100}{1 + 100(0.05)^3} = \frac{100}{1 + 100(0.000125)}$ $= \frac{100}{1 + 0.0125} = \frac{100}{1.0125}$ <p>= 98.7</p> <p>$SS = \underline{99}$</p>

	<p> $SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$ </p> <p>For population ranging between 1 – 8,000 (Which is the most widely used)</p>	<p>OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 99 staff of the Operations department since the OST result give 98.7 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p> <p>Finance and Accounts Staff: 10</p> $SS = \frac{10}{1 + 10(0.05)^3} = \frac{10}{1 + 10(0.000125)}$ $= \frac{10}{1 + 0.00125} = \frac{10}{1.00125}$ $= 9.9$ <p>SS = <u>10</u></p> <p>OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 10 staff of the Finance and Accounts department since the OST result give 9.9 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p> <p>Human Resources Staff: 58</p> $SS = \frac{58}{1 + 58(0.05)^3} = \frac{58}{1 + 58(0.000125)}$ $= \frac{58}{1 + 0.00725} = \frac{58}{1.00725}$ $= 57.5$ <p>SS = <u>58</u></p> <p>OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 58 staff of the Human Resources department since the OST result give 57.5 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal</p>
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		<p>then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p> <p>Legal Staff: 20</p> $SS = \frac{20}{1 + 20(0.05)^3} = \frac{20}{1 + 20(0.000125)}$ $= \frac{20}{1 + 0.0025} = \frac{20}{1.0025}$ $= 19.9$ <p>SS = <u>20</u></p> <p>OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 20 staff of the Legal department since the OST result gives 19,9 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p>
<p>The Fifth Procedure:</p>	<p>After the sample has been gotten for the branches, departments and no of staff, then:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. apply the no of sample gotten to other related departments as in the Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 1, however, ii. if the departments and staff have different numbers (not equal), then the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) should be applicable to each departments and staff. <p>Check: “Understanding the Stages of Olonite Diagram Representing The Complete Set 2”</p>

Source: Author’s Computation and Design, 2021

The Olonite Diagram (OD) and Table can as well be a Country, State, Cities, Communities, Institution, Universities, etc.

3.3. UNDERSTANDING THE PROCEDURES/STAGES OF OLONITE DIAGRAM REPRESENTING THE COMPLETE SET 2

For example: An organization X has 3 branches; E, F and G have three to four departments (Operations, Finance and Accounts, Human Resources and legal) i.e. 45, 7 and 20 staff respectively for branch E, 46, 10 and 21 staff respectively for branch F and 23, 14, 18 and 20 staff respectively for branch G. The number of staff in each department of each branch are not the same, therefore, the Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 2 is valid for organization X and the procedures/stages 1 – 5 should be followed.

As a researcher you are to sample from organization X total population which has 224 population. Directly sampling from the 188 total population will not give equal representation hence the Five (5) procedures/stages is advised as seen below:

Table 2: The Five Tabulated Stages of Olonite Proportional Allocation Method for the Olonite Diagram 2

Stages	To Do 1	To Do 2
The First procedure:	Study the organization to know the version of the Olonite Diagram that best fit into the organization settings.	Check which of the Olonite Diagrams best fit the organization in view
The Second Procedure:	Apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the branches to sample. For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001, SS = $\frac{TP}{3}$	3 Branches (E, F, and G) SS = $\frac{3}{1 + 3(0.05)3} = \frac{3}{1 + 3(0.000125)}$ $= \frac{3}{1 + 0.000375} = 2.99$ SS = $\frac{3}{1 + 0.000375} = 1.000375$

	$1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3$ <p>For population ranging between 1 – 8,000 (Which is the most widely used)</p>	<p>OPAM suggests the use of all the four branches since the OST result give 2.99 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p>
<p>The Third Procedure:</p>	<p>After the branches sample has been gotten, apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the departments to sample.</p> <p>For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001,</p> $SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$ <p>For population ranging between 1 – 8,000 (Which is the most widely used)</p>	<p>3 Departments (Operations, Finance and Accounts, Human Resources), Branch E and F.</p> $SS = \frac{3}{1 + 3(0.05)^3} = \frac{3}{1 + 3(0.000125)}$ $= \frac{3}{1 + 0.000375} = \frac{3}{1.000375}$ <p>= 2.99</p> <p>SS = <u>3</u></p> <p>OPAM suggests the use of all the four departments since the OST result give 2.99 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p> <p>4 Departments (Operations, Finance and Accounts, Human Resources and legal), Branch G.</p> $SS = \frac{4}{1 + 4(0.05)^3} = \frac{4}{1 + 4(0.000125)}$ $= \frac{4}{1 + 0.0005} = \frac{4}{1.0005}$ <p>= 3.99</p> <p>SS = <u>4</u></p>

		<p>OPAM suggests the use of all the four departments since the OST result give 3.99 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p>
<p>The Fourth Procedure:</p>	<p>After the department sample has been gotten, apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the number of staff to sample.</p> <p>For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001,</p> $SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$ <p>For population ranging between 1 – 8,000 (Which is the most widely used)</p>	<p>Branch E (3 Departments)</p> <p>Operations Staff: 45:</p> $SS = \frac{45}{1 + 45(0.05)^3} = \frac{45}{1 + 45(0.000125)}$ $= \frac{45}{1 + 0.005625} = \frac{45}{1.005625}$ <p>= 44.7</p> <p>SS = <u>45</u></p> <p>OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 45 staff of the Operations department since the OST result give 44.7 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p> <p>Finance and Accounts Staff: 7</p> $SS = \frac{7}{1 + 7(0.05)^3} = \frac{7}{1 + 7(0.000125)}$ $= \frac{7}{1 + 0.000875} = \frac{7}{1.000875}$ <p>= 6.9</p> <p>SS = <u>7</u></p> <p>OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 7 staff of the Finance and Accounts department since the OST result give 6.9 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal</p>

then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.

Human Resources Staff: 20

$$\begin{aligned}
 SS &= \frac{20}{1 + 20(0.05)^3} = \frac{20}{1 + 20(0.000125)} \\
 &= \frac{20}{1 + 0.0025} = \frac{20}{1.0025} \\
 &= 19.9
 \end{aligned}$$

SS = 20

OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 20 staff of the Human Resources department since the OST result give 19.9 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.

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Branch F: (3 Departments)

Operations Staff: 46:

$$\begin{aligned}
 SS &= \frac{46}{1 + 46(0.05)^3} = \frac{46}{1 + 46(0.000125)} \\
 &= \frac{46}{1 + 0.00575} = \frac{46}{1.000575} \\
 &= 45.7
 \end{aligned}$$

SS = 46

OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 46 staff of the Operations department since the OST result give 45.7 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.

	<p>Finance and Accounts Staff: 10</p> $SS = \frac{10}{1 + 10(0.05)^3} = \frac{10}{1 + 10(0.00125)}$ $= \frac{10}{1 + 0.0125} = \frac{10}{1.0125}$ <p>= 9.9</p> <p>SS = <u>10</u></p> <p>OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 10 staff of the Finance and Accounts department since the OST result give 9.9 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p> <p>Human Resources Staff: 21</p> $SS = \frac{21}{1 + 21(0.05)^3} = \frac{21}{1 + 21(0.00125)}$ $= \frac{21}{1 + 0.02625} = \frac{21}{1.02625}$ <p>= 20.9</p> <p>SS = <u>21</u></p> <p>OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 21 staff of the Human Resources department since the OST result give 20.9 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p> <p>.....</p> <p>Branch G (4 Departments)</p> <p>Operations Staff: 23:</p> $SS = \frac{23}{1 + 23(0.05)^3} = \frac{23}{1 + 23(0.00125)}$
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		$= \frac{1 + 23(0.05)^3}{1 + 0.002875} = \frac{1 + 23(0.000125)}{1.002875}$ $= \frac{23}{1.002875}$ $= 22.9$ <p>SS = <u>23</u></p> <p>OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 23 staff of the Operations department since the OST result give 22.9 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p> <p>Finance and Accounts Staff: 14</p> $SS = \frac{14}{1 + 14(0.05)^3} = \frac{14}{1 + 14(0.000125)}$ $= \frac{14}{1 + 0.00175} = \frac{14}{1.00175}$ $= 13.9$ <p>SS = <u>14</u></p> <p>OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 14 staff of the Finance and Accounts department since the OST result give 13.9 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p> <p>Human Resources Staff: 18</p> $SS = \frac{18}{1 + 18(0.05)^3} = \frac{18}{1 + 18(0.000125)}$ $= \frac{18}{1 + 0.00225} = \frac{18}{1.00225}$ $= 17.9$
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		<p>SS = <u>18</u></p> <p>OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 18 staff of the Human Resources department since the OST result give 17.9 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p> <p>Legal Staff: 20</p> $SS = \frac{20}{1 + 20(0.05)^3} = \frac{20}{1 + 20(0.00125)}$ $= \frac{20}{1 + 0.0025} = \frac{20}{1.0025}$ <p>= 19.9</p> <p>SS = <u>20</u></p> <p>OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 20 staff of the Legal department since the OST result gives 19,9 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p>
The Fifth Procedure:	After the sample has been gotten for the branches, departments and no of staff, then:	i. if the departments and staff have different numbers (not equal), then the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) should be applicable to each departments and staff unlike the “i” in the fifth Procedure and added together to get the total sample size.

Source: Author’s Computation and Design, 2021

The Olonite Diagram (OD) and Table can as well be a Country, State, Cities, Communities, Institution, Universities, etc.

3.4. UNDERSTANDING THE PROCEDURES/STAGES OF OLONITE DIAGRAM REPRESENTING THE COMPLETE SET 3

For example: An organization Z has 1 branch; H which have four departments (Operations, Finance and Accounts, Human Resources and legal) i.e. 100, 10, 58 and 20 respectively. The organization only has 1 branch therefore, the Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 1 is valid for organization Z and the procedures/stages 1 – 5 should be followed.

As a researcher you are to sample from organization Z total population which has 188 population. Directly sampling from the 188 total population will not give equal representation hence the Five (5) procedures/stages is advised as seen below:

Table 3: The Five Tabulated Stages of Olonite Proportional Allocation Method for the Olonite Diagram 3

Stages	To Do 1	To Do 2
The First procedure:	Study the organization to know the version of the Olonite Diagram that best fit into the organization settings.	Check which of the Olonite Diagrams best fit the organization in view
The Second Procedure:	Apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the branches to sample. For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001, $SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)3}$	-

	For population ranging between 1 – 8,000 (Which is the most widely used)	
The Third Procedure:	<p>After the branches sample has been gotten, apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the departments to sample.</p> <p>For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001,</p> $SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$ <p>For population ranging between 1 – 8,000 (Which is the most widely used)</p>	<p>4 Departments (Operations, Finance and Accounts, Human Resources and legal), Branch H.</p> $SS = \frac{4}{1 + 4(0.05)^3} = \frac{4}{1 + 4(0.000125)}$ $= \frac{4}{1 + 0.005} = \frac{4}{1.0005}$ <p>= 3.99</p> <p>SS = <u>4</u></p> <p>OPAM suggests the use of all the four departments since the OST result give 3.99 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p>
The Fourth Procedure:	<p>After the department sample has been gotten, apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the number of staff to sample.</p> <p>For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001,</p> $SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$ <p>For population ranging between 1 – 8,000 (Which is the most widely used)</p>	<p>Branch H (4 Departments)</p> <p>Operations Staff: 100:</p> $SS = \frac{100}{1 + 100(0.05)^3} = \frac{100}{1 + 100(0.000125)}$ $= \frac{100}{1 + 0.0125} = \frac{100}{1.0125}$ <p>= 98.7</p> <p>SS = <u>99</u></p> <p>OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 99 staff of the Operations department since the OST result give 98.7 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p>

Finance and Accounts Staff: 10

$$\begin{aligned}SS &= \frac{10}{1 + 10(0.05)^3} = \frac{10}{1 + 10(0.000125)} \\ &= \frac{10}{1 + 0.00125} = \frac{10}{1.00125} \\ &= 9.9\end{aligned}$$

SS = 10

OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 10 staff of the Finance and Accounts department since the OST result give 9.9 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.

Human Resources Staff: 58

$$\begin{aligned}SS &= \frac{58}{1 + 58(0.05)^3} = \frac{58}{1 + 58(0.000125)} \\ &= \frac{58}{1 + 0.00725} = \frac{58}{1.00725} \\ &= 57.5\end{aligned}$$

SS = 58

OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 58 staff of the Human Resources department since the OST result give 57.5 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.

Legal Staff: 20

$$\begin{aligned}SS &= \frac{20}{1 + 20(0.05)^3} = \frac{20}{1 + 20(0.000125)}\end{aligned}$$

		$= \frac{20}{1 + 0.0025} = \frac{20}{1.0025}$ $= 19.9$ $SS = \underline{20}$ <p>OPAM suggests that the researcher should sample 20 staff of the Legal department since the OST result gives 19,9 and when the SS shows a number with a decimal then, it must be rounded up to the nearest whole number.</p>
The Fifth Procedure:	After the sample has been gotten for the branches, departments and no of staff, then:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. apply the no of sample gotten to other related departments as in the Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 1, however, ii. if the departments and staff have different numbers (not equal), then the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) should be applicable to each departments and staff. <p>Check: “Understanding the Stages of Olonite Diagram Representing The Complete Set 2”</p>

Source: Author’s Computation and Design, 2021
The Olonite Diagram (OD) and Table can as well be a Country, State, Cities, Communities, Institution, Universities, etc.

3.5. UNDERSTANDING THE PROCEDURES/STAGES OF OLONITE DIAGRAM REPRESENTING THE COMPLETE SET 4

For example: An organization Y has 4 know branches; A, B, C and D (Operations, Finance and Accounts, Human Resources and legal) and others not captured represented by Y¹ the known branches having 100, 10, 58 and 20 staff respectively. The number of staff in each department of each branch are the same for the know branches but different to the Y¹ therefore, the Olonite

Diagram representing the Complete Set 1 is valid for organization Y and the procedures/stages 1 – 5 should be followed.

As a researcher you are to sample from organization Y total population which has 188 population + x (Y¹). Directly sampling from the 188 total population will not give equal representation hence the Five (5) procedures/stages is advised as seen below:

Table 4: The Five Tabulated Stages of Olonite Proportional Allocation Method for the Olonite Diagram 4

Stages	To Do 1	To Do 2
The First procedure:	Study the organization to know the version of the Olonite Diagram that best fit into the organization settings.	Check Table 1
The Second Procedure:	Apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the branches to sample. For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001, $SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)3}$ For population ranging between 1 – 8,000 (Which is the most widely used)	Check Table 1
The Third Procedure:	After the branches sample has been gotten, apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the departments to sample.	

	<p>For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001,</p> $SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$ <p>For population ranging between 1 – 8,000 (Which is the most widely used)</p>	<p>Check Table 1</p>
<p>The Fourth Procedure:</p>	<p>After the department sample has been gotten, apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the number of staff to sample.</p> <p>For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001,</p> $SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$ <p>For population ranging between 1 – 8,000 (Which is the most widely used)</p>	<p>Check Table 1</p>
<p>The Fifth Procedure:</p>	<p>After the sample has been gotten for the branches, departments and no of staff, then:</p>	<p>i. apply the no of sample gotten to other related departments as in the Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 1, and</p> <p>ii. since there are other departments and staff have that are different from the 4 known branches, (not equal), then the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) should be applicable to each departments and staff. Check: “Understanding the Stages of</p>

		Olonite Diagram Representing The Complete Set 2”
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Source: Author’s Computation and Design, 2021

The Olonite Diagram (OD) and Table can as well be a Country, State, Cities, Communities, Institution, Universities, etc.

Note: The complement of Y, written Y^1 , contains all events in the sample space which are not members of I, J, K and L. I, J, K and L and Y^1 together cover every possible eventuality which are other branches not covered.

Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 4 informs that an organisation having more branches having the same number of department and staff while the headquarters department and staff slightly differs to all the branch can be represented with the OD Complete Set 4.

3.6. UNDERSTANDING THE PROCEDURES/STAGES OF OLONITE DIAGRAM REPRESENTING THE COMPLETE SET 5

For example: An organization P has 3 known branches; M, N and O with 3-4 (Operations, Finance, Accounts, Human Resources and Legal) and others not captured represented by Y^1 the known branches having 48, 7, 20; 46, 10, 21 and 23, 14, 18 and 20 staff respectively. The number of staff in each department of each branch are not the same for the known branches and also different to the P^1 therefore, the Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 5 is valid for organization P and the procedures/stages 1 – 5 should be followed.

As a researcher you are to sample from organization P total population which has 227 population + x (P^1) directly sampling from the 227 total population will not give equal representation hence the Five (5) procedures/stages is advised as seen below:

Table 5: The Five Tabulated Stages of Olonite Proportional Allocation Method for the Olonite Diagram 5

Stages	To Do 1	To Do 2
The First procedure:	Study the organization to know the version of the Olonite Diagram that best fit into the organization settings.	Check Table 2
The Second Procedure:	<p>Apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the branches to sample.</p> <p>For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001,</p> $SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$ <p>For population ranging between 1 – 8,000 (Which is the most widely used)</p>	Check Table 2
The Third Procedure:	<p>After the branches sample has been gotten, apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the departments to sample.</p> <p>For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001,</p> $SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$	Check Table 2

	For population ranging between 1 – 8,000 (Which is the most widely used)	
The Fourth Procedure:	<p>After the department sample has been gotten, apply the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) for the selection of the number of staff to sample.</p> <p>For Level of Significance: 0.15, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01, 0.002 & 0.001,</p> $SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL)^3}$ <p>For population ranging between 1 – 8,000 (Which is the most widely used)</p>	Check Table 2
The Fifth Procedure:	<p>After the sample has been gotten for the branches, departments and no of staff, then:</p>	<p>i. apply the no of sample gotten to other related departments as in the Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 1, and</p> <p>ii. since there are other departments and staff have that are different from the 4 known branches, (not equal), then the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) should be applicable to each departments and staff.</p> <p>Check: “Understanding the Stages of Olonite Diagram Representing The Complete Set 2”</p>

Source: Author’s Computation and Design, 2021
The Olonite Diagram (OD) and Table can as well be a Country, State, Cities, Communities, Institution, Universities, etc.

Note: The complement of P, written P^1 , contains all events in the sample space which are not members of M, N and O. M, N, and O and P^1 together cover every possible eventuality.

Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 5 informs that an organisation having more branches having the same number of department and staff while the headquarters department and staff slightly differs to all the branch can be represented with the OD Complete Set 5.

4. DISCUSSION

The Olonite Diagram representing the Complete Set 1 shows that when an organization has equal no of departments in each branch and staff in each department, then whatever applies to a branch is applicable to all, therefore as seen in table 1 where branch A has 4 departments and equal number of staff as in the case of other branches B, C and D then the sampling size applicable to branch A, applies to branch B, C and D as well.

For Branch A, we have a sample size of 4 Departments, 99 staff in the Operations Department, 10 staff in the Finance and Accounts, 58 staff in the Human Resources Department and 20 staff in the Legal Department which means that the same sample size should be applicable to branch A, B, C and D respectively. This ease stress of recalculation and saves time.

However, if the departments and staff have different numbers (not equal), then the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) should be applicable to each departments and staff unlike the “i” in the fifth Procedure and added together to get the total sample size.

It should be noted that when the Olonite Diagram shows Y (Y^1) or P (P^1) it means that the complement of Y and P, written as Y^1 and P^1 , contains all events in the sample space which together cover every possible eventuality. This denotes that Y^1 and P^1 are not members of the branches, departments and staff but a member of the Olonite Diagram (OD). Y^1 and P^1 can be

branches, departments or staff. It is used to denote an Organization that has more branches in strategic places.

This sort of allocation is true for the population where the variable under consideration is not receiving/ attracting any external influence and if it so, then it is equal for all units of the population.

5. CONCLUSION

Olonite Proportional Allocation Method is a suitable proportional Allocation Method to be considered when sampling organizations with branches. The method has been seen as an advanced means of allocating proportionally, samples to population of stratum/strata with equal number or with different sub population.

The Olonite Diagram (OD) and Table can as well be a Country, State, Cities, Communities, Institutions, Universities, etc. depending on the aim of the researcher.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

i. The Olonite Proportional Allocation Method (OPAM) is encouraged to be used by Countries, Governments, Organizations, Researchers, Research Departments, Universities, States, etc since it makes allocation proportionally done.

ii. The procedures/stages in the Olonite Proportional Allocation Method should be studied and followed truthfully to achieve an unbiased results.

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